

**THE MEAN VALUE OF A HYBRID ARITHMETIC FUNCTION
ASSOCIATED TO FOURIER COEFFICIENTS OF CUSP FORMS**

Linli Wei

*School of Mathematics and Statistics, Shandong Normal University, Ji'nan,
Shandong, P. R. China
2576599154@qq.com*

Huixue Lao

*School of Mathematics and Statistics, Shandong Normal University, Ji'nan,
Shandong, P. R. China
lhxsdu@163.com*

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Abstract

Let $\lambda_f(n)$, $\sigma(n)$, and $\phi(n)$ denote the n^{th} Fourier coefficient of holomorphic cusp form f , the sum-of-divisors function, and the Euler totient function, respectively. We improve the error term of the asymptotic formula of $\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^j(n) \sigma^b(n) \phi^c(n)$ for $j = 2, 4, 6$, and estimate the sum $\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^j(n) \sigma^b(n) \phi^c(n)$ for $j = 7, 8$.

1. Introduction

In analytic number theory, one of the most basic goals is to establish the asymptotic formulae for the summation function

$$S(x) = \sum_{n \leq x} a(n),$$

where $a(n)$ is an arithmetic function. In this paper, we investigate a hybrid arithmetic function $\lambda_f^j(n) \sigma^b(n) \phi^c(n)$, where $\lambda_f(n)$ is the n -th Fourier coefficient of holomorphic cusp form f , $\sigma(n)$ is the sum-of-divisors function, and $\phi(n)$ is the Euler totient function.

Assume that k is an even integer and H_k^* is the set of all normalized Hecke primitive eigencuspform of weight k for the full modular group $SL_2(\mathbb{Z})$. The Fourier expansion of $f \in H_k^*$ at $z = \infty$ is

$$f(z) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \lambda_f(n) n^{\frac{k-1}{2}} e(z).$$

Here, $\lambda_f(n)$ is the eigenvalue of Hecke operator T_n , and $\lambda_f(n)$ is real and satisfies the multiplicative property

$$\lambda_f(m)\lambda_f(n) = \sum_{d|(m,n)} \lambda_f\left(\frac{mn}{d^2}\right),$$

where $m \geq 1$ and $n \geq 1$ are arbitrary integers. Fourier coefficients of holomorphic cusp forms are extremely significant and are of interest to many mathematicians. In 1974, Deligne [4] proved the Ramanujan-Petersson conjecture

$$|\lambda_f(n)| \leq d(n), \tag{1.1}$$

where $d(n)$ is the Dirichlet divisor function.

Rankin [17] studied the sum of Fourier coefficients of cusp forms over natural numbers, and showed that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f(n) \ll x^{1/3}(\log x)^{-\delta},$$

where $0 < \delta < 0.06$. In 1990, Ivić [5] obtained the following result:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^2(n) = cx + O_f(x^{\frac{3}{8}}).$$

Recently, Manski, Mayle and Zbacnik [15] investigated a hybrid arithmetic function and showed

$$\sum_{n \leq x} d^a(n)\sigma^b(n)\phi^c(n) = x^{b+c+1}P_{2\alpha-1}(\log x) + O(x^{b+c+r_a+\varepsilon}),$$

where a, b, c are real numbers, $\frac{1}{2} \leq r_a < 1$, and $P_n(t)$ is a polynomial of degree n .

Subsequently, the mean values of the hybrid arithmetic function $\lambda_f^i(n)\sigma^b(n)\phi^c(n)$ were estimated by Li[14] for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, and by Cui[3] for $i = 5, 6$.

Combining the classical analytic method with properties of some primitive automorphic L-functions, we improve the results of $\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^i(n)\sigma^b(n)\phi^c(n)$ for $i = 2, 4, 6$, and further study the summation $\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^i(n)\sigma^b(n)\phi^c(n)$ for $i = 7, 8$. In detail, we obtain the following results.

Theorem 1. *Let $b, c \in \mathbb{R}$, $f \in H_k^*$, and let $\lambda_f(n)$ denote its n -th normalized Fourier coefficient. Then for any $\varepsilon > 0$,*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^2(n)\sigma^b(n)\phi^c(n) = C_0x^{b+c+1} + O\left(x^{b+c+\frac{23}{37}+\varepsilon}\right),$$

where the O -constant depends on f .

Theorem 2. Let $b, c \in \mathbb{R}$, $f \in H_k^*$, and let $\lambda_f(n)$ denote its n -th normalized Fourier coefficient. Then for any $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^4(n) \sigma^b(n) \phi^c(n) = x^{b+c+1} P_1(\log x) + O\left(x^{b+c+\frac{257}{299}+\varepsilon}\right),$$

where $P_1(t)$ is a polynomial in t of degree 1, and the O -constant depends on f .

Theorem 3. Let $b, c \in \mathbb{R}$, $f \in H_k^*$, and let $\lambda_f(n)$ denote its n -th normalized Fourier coefficient. Then for any $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^6(n) \sigma^b(n) \phi^c(n) = x^{b+c+1} P_4(\log x) + O\left(x^{b+c+\frac{201}{208}+\varepsilon}\right),$$

where $P_4(t)$ is a polynomial in t of degree 4, and the O -constant depends on f .

Remark. We improve the results in [3, Theorem 4], [14, Theorem 2] and [14, Theorem 4] respectively. By comparison, $23/37 = 0.621 \dots < 38/59 = 0.644 \dots$ ([14, Theorem 2]), $257/299 = 0.8595 \dots < 139/160 = 0.86875$ ([14, Theorem 4]), $201/208 = 0.9663 \dots < 631/652 = 0.9677 \dots$ ([3, Theorem 4]).

Theorem 4. Let $b, c \in \mathbb{R}$, $f \in H_k^*$, and let $\lambda_f(n)$ denote its n -th normalized Fourier coefficient. Then for any $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^7(n) \sigma^b(n) \phi^c(n) = O\left(x^{b+c+\frac{87}{88}+\varepsilon}\right),$$

where the O -constant depends on f .

Theorem 5. Let $b, c \in \mathbb{R}$, $f \in H_k^*$, and let $\lambda_f(n)$ denote its n -th normalized Fourier coefficient. Then for any $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^8(n) \sigma^b(n) \phi^c(n) = x^{b+c+1} P_{13}(\log x) + O\left(x^{b+c+\frac{117}{118}+\varepsilon}\right),$$

where $P_{13}(t)$ is a polynomial in t of degree 13, and the O -constant depends on f .

2. Preliminaries

In order to prove Theorems 1-5, some relevant results will be given in this section. First, we will introduce several primitive automorphic L-functions.

The definition of the Riemann zeta function is

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \prod_p (1 - p^{-s})^{-1}, \quad \text{Re}(s) > 1. \tag{2.1}$$

The Hecke L -function of $f \in H_k^*$ is a Dirichlet series and has Euler product representation

$$L(f, s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_f(n)n^{-s} = \prod_p (1 - \alpha_f(p)p^{-s})^{-1}(1 - \beta_f(p)p^{-s})^{-1}, \tag{2.2}$$

where $\alpha_f(p)$ and $\beta_f(p)$ are called local roots or local parameters of $L(f, s)$ at p . According to Deligne [10], they satisfy

$$\lambda_f(p) = \alpha_f(p) + \beta_f(p), |\alpha_f(p)| = |\beta_f(p)| = \alpha_f(p)\beta_f(p) = 1. \tag{2.3}$$

The inequality (1.1) ensures that the Dirichlet series (2.2) is absolutely convergent for $\text{Re}(s) > 1$.

The j th symmetric power L -function attached to $f \in H_k^*$ is defined as

$$L(\text{sym}^j f, s) := \prod_p \prod_{m=0}^j (1 - \alpha_f(p)^{j-m}\beta_f(p)^m p^{-s})^{-1}. \tag{2.4}$$

The definition of Rankin-Selberg L -function shows that

$$L(\text{sym}^i f \times \text{sym}^j f, s) := \prod_p \prod_{m=0}^i \prod_{u=0}^j (1 - \alpha_f(p)^{(i+j)-2(m+u)} p^{-s})^{-1}. \tag{2.5}$$

The above products over primes give the Dirichlet series for $L(\text{sym}^j f, s)$ and $L(\text{sym}^i f \times \text{sym}^j f, s)$. In view of (2.3)-(2.5), it is easy to see that $L(\text{sym}^j f, s)$ and $L(\text{sym}^i f \times \text{sym}^j f, s)$ converge absolutely in half-plane $\text{Re}(s) > 1$.

Now we give the current best subconvexity (or convexity) bounds of these primitive automorphic L -functions.

The proofs of the statements in the following lemma may be found in [1], [6, Chapter 5], and [16].

Lemma 2.1. *For any $\varepsilon > 0$, $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 1$, and $|t| \geq 2$, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(\sigma + it) &\ll_{\varepsilon} (1 + |t|)^{\max\{\frac{13}{42}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon}, \\ L(\text{sym}^2 f, \sigma + it) &\ll_{f, \varepsilon} (1 + |t|)^{\max\{\frac{4}{3}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon}, \\ L(\text{sym}^j f, \sigma + it) &\ll_{f, \varepsilon} (1 + |t|)^{\max\{\frac{j+1}{2}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon}, \quad j = 3, 4, \end{aligned}$$

$$L(\text{sym}^i f \times \text{sym}^j f, \sigma + it) \ll_{f,\varepsilon} (1 + |t|)^{\max\{\frac{(i+1)(j+1)}{2}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4.$$

The following lemma describes the mean-value of symmetric power L-functions and their Rankin-Selberg L-functions.

Lemma 2.2. *For $i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4$, any $\varepsilon > 0$, $T \geq T_0$ (where T_0 is sufficiently large), we have the estimates*

$$\int_T^{2T} \left| L\left(\text{sym}^j f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it\right) \right|^2 dt \ll_{f,\varepsilon} T^{\frac{j+1}{2} + \varepsilon},$$

$$\int_T^{2T} \left| L\left(\text{sym}^i f \times \text{sym}^j f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it\right) \right|^2 dt \ll_{f,\varepsilon} T^{\frac{(i+1)(j+1)}{2} + \varepsilon}.$$

Proof. The first assertion is in [10, Lemma 2.5], and the second is in [11, Lemma 2.4]. □

Now we introduce the Perron’s formula, which is proved in [9, section 1.2.1].

Lemma 2.3. *Let $F(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{a(n)}{n^s}$ and $a(n) \leq A(n)$, and the series of $F(s)$ converges absolutely for $\sigma > 1$, where $A(n)$ is monotonically increasing function and $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{a(n)}{n^s} = O\left(\frac{1}{(\sigma-1)^\alpha}\right)$ with $\sigma \rightarrow 1^+$. If $b > 1$ and $x = N + \frac{1}{2}$ with $N \in \mathbb{N}$. Then for $T \geq 2$,*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} a(n) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{b-iT}^{b+iT} F(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x^b}{T(b-1)^\alpha} + \frac{x A(2x) \log x}{T}\right).$$

Lemma 2.4. *Let $f \in H_k^*$ and $\lambda_f(n)$ denote its n^{th} normalized Fourier coefficient. Define*

$$F_1(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_f^7(n) \sigma^b(n) \phi^c(n)}{n^s}.$$

Then $F_1(s)$ can be factored as

$$F_1(s) = L(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^3 f, s - b - c) L^5(\text{sym}^3 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c) \\ \times L^8(\text{sym}^3 f, s - b - c) L^8(f, s - b - c) H_1(s),$$

where $H_1(s)$ is absolutely convergent in $\text{Re}(s) > b + c + \frac{1}{2}$.

Proof. Because each of $\lambda_f(n)$, $\sigma(n)$, and $\phi(n)$ are multiplicative, $\lambda_f^7(n)\sigma^b(n)\phi^c(n)$ is multiplicative. Therefore, the Dirichlet series $F_1(s)$ can be rewritten as a product over primes:

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(s) &= \prod_p f_{1,p}(s) = \prod_p \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_f^7(p^k)\sigma^b(p^k)\phi^c(p^k)}{p^{ks}} \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_f^7(p)\sigma^b(p)\phi^c(p)}{p^s} + \frac{\lambda_f^7(p^2)\sigma^b(p^2)\phi^c(p^2)}{p^{2s}} + \dots \right). \end{aligned}$$

From the theory of Hecke operators, we obtain the recursive relation

$$\lambda_f(p^j) = \lambda_f(p^{j-1})\lambda_f(p) - \lambda_f(p^{j-2}), \quad j \geq 2.$$

By induction, we have

$$\lambda_f(p^j) = \frac{\alpha_f(p)^{j+1} - \beta_f(p)^{j+1}}{\alpha_f(p) - \beta_f(p)} = \sum_{m=0}^j \alpha_f(p)^{j-m} \beta_f(p)^m.$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} f_{1,p}(s) &= 1 + \frac{(\alpha_f(p) + \beta_f(p))^7 (p+1)^b (p-1)^c}{p^s} \\ &\quad + \frac{\left(\frac{\alpha_f^3(p) - \beta_f^3(p)}{\alpha_f(p) - \beta_f(p)}\right)^7 (p^2 + p + 1)^b (p^2 - p)^c}{p^{2s}} + \dots \\ &= 1 + \frac{(\alpha_f(p) + \beta_f(p))^7 (p+1)^b (p-1)^c}{p^s} \\ &\quad + \frac{\left(\alpha_f^2(p) + \alpha_f(p)\beta_f(p) + \beta_f^2(p)\right)^7 (p^2 + p + 1)^b (p^2 - p)^c}{p^{2s}} + \dots \\ &= 1 + \frac{(\alpha_f(p) + \beta_f(p))^7}{p^{s-b-c}} + O\left(p^{2(b+c-\sigma)} + p^{(b+c-\sigma-1)}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_1(s) &= \prod_p f_{1,p}(s) \\
 &= \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{(\alpha_f(p) + \beta_f(p))^7}{p^{s-b-c}} + O\left(p^{2(b+c-\sigma)} + p^{(b+c-\sigma-1)}\right) \right) \\
 &= \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{\alpha_f^7(p) + 7\alpha_f^5(p) + 21\alpha_f^3(p) + 35\alpha_f(p) + 35\beta_f(p) + 21\beta_f^3(p) + 7\beta_f^5(p) + \beta_f^7(p)}{p^{s-b-c}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + O\left(p^{2(b+c-\sigma)} + p^{(b+c-\sigma-1)}\right) \right) \\
 &= L(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^3 f, s - b - c) \\
 &\quad \times \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{5\alpha_f^5(p) + 18\alpha_f^3(p) + 31\alpha_f(p) + 31\beta_f(p) + 18\beta_f^3(p) + 5\beta_f^5(p)}{p^{s-b-c}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + O\left(p^{2(b+c-\sigma)} + p^{(b+c-\sigma-1)}\right) \right) \\
 &= L(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^3 f, s - b - c)L^5(\text{sym}^3 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c) \\
 &\quad \times \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{8\alpha_f^3(p) + 16\alpha_f(p) + 16\beta_f(p) + 8\beta_f^3(p)}{p^{s-b-c}} + O\left(p^{2(b+c-\sigma)} + p^{(b+c-\sigma-1)}\right) \right) \\
 &= L(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^3 f, s - b - c)L^5(\text{sym}^3 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c)L^8(\text{sym}^3 f, s - b - c) \\
 &\quad \times \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{8\alpha_f(p) + 8\beta_f(p)}{p^{s-b-c}} + O\left(p^{2(b+c-\sigma)} + p^{(b+c-\sigma-1)}\right) \right) \\
 &= L(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^3 f, s - b - c)L^5(\text{sym}^3 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c)L^8(\text{sym}^3 f, s - b - c) \\
 &\quad \times L^8(f, s - b - c) \prod_p \left(1 + O\left(p^{2(b+c-\sigma)} + p^{(b+c-\sigma-1)}\right) \right) \\
 &= L(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^3 f, s - b - c)L^5(\text{sym}^3 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c)L^8(\text{sym}^3 f, s - b - c) \\
 &\quad \times L^8(f, s - b - c)H_1(s),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $H_1(s)$ is absolutely convergent in $Re(s) > b + c + \frac{1}{2}$. □

The proof of the following lemma is similar to that of Lemma 2.4.

Lemma 2.5. *Let $f \in H_k^*$ and $\lambda_f(n)$ denote its n -th normalized Fourier coefficient. Define*

$$F_2(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_f^8(n)\sigma^b(n)\phi^c(n)}{n^s}.$$

Then $F_2(s)$ can be factored as

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_2(s) &= L(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^4 f, s - b - c)L^6(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c) \\
 &\quad \times L^{13}(\text{sym}^4 f, s - b - c)L^{21}(\text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c)\zeta^{13}(s - b - c)H_2(s),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $H_2(s)$ is absolutely convergent in $Re(s) > b + c + \frac{1}{2}$.

3. Proofs of Theorems 1-5

The proofs of Theorems 1-5 are similar, so we just prove Theorem 5 in this section.

Proof of Theorem 5. Denote $\lambda_f^8(n)\sigma^b(n)\phi^c(n)$ by $f_2(n)$. From (1.1), we observe that $f_2(n) \leq Bn^{b+c+\varepsilon}$, where B is a real constant on ε . Let

$$L_2(f, s - b - c) = L(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^4 f, s - b - c)L^6(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c) \\ \times L^{13}(\text{sym}^4 f, s - b - c)L^{21}(\text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c)\zeta^{13}(s - b - c).$$

From Lemma 2.5, we learn that $F_2(s) = L_2(f, s - b - c)H_2(s)$.

From the works of Cogdell and Mochel [2], Jacquet and Shalika [7] [8], Shahidi [19] [20], and the reformulation of Rudnick and Sarnak [18], symmetric power L-function $L(\text{sym}^i f, s)$ ($1 \leq i \leq 4$) and Rankin-Selberg L-function $L(\text{sym}^i f \times \text{sym}^j f, s)$ ($1 \leq i < j \leq 4$) can be extended to be an entire function on the whole complex plane. Lau and Wu [12] showed that for $1 \leq j \leq 4$, $L(\text{sym}^j f \times \text{sym}^j f, s)$ is entire except possible for simple poles at $s = 0, 1$, and satisfies a functional equation. Thus, $F_2(s)$ can be analytically continued to the half-plane $Re(s) > b + c + \frac{1}{2}$. In this region, $F_2(s)$ only has a pole $s = b + c + 1$ of order 14.

By using Lemma 2.3 (Perron’s formula), we obtain

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^8(n)\sigma^b(n)\phi^c(n) \\ = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{b+c+1+\varepsilon-iT}^{b+c+1+\varepsilon+iT} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{f_2(n)}{n^s} \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x^{1+\varepsilon}}{T^{s-b-c-1}}\right) + O\left(\frac{x B(2x)^{b+c+\varepsilon} \log x}{T}\right) \\ = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{b+c+1+\varepsilon-iT}^{b+c+1+\varepsilon+iT} L_2(f, s - b - c)H_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x^{b+c+1+\varepsilon}}{T}\right), \tag{3.1}$$

where T with $1 \leq T \leq x$ is a parameter to be specified later.

Since our goal is to estimate the integral in (3.1), we need to consider the closed contour Γ :

$$I = [b + c + 1 + \varepsilon - iT, b + c + 1 + \varepsilon + iT], \\ II = [b + c + 1 + \varepsilon + iT, b + c + \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + iT], \\ III = [b + c + \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + iT, b + c + \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon - iT], \\ IV = [b + c + \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon - iT, b + c + 1 + \varepsilon - iT].$$

Let

$$I_1 = \int_I L_2(f, s - b - c)H_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds, \quad I_2 = \int_{II} L_2(f, s - b - c)H_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds, \\ I_3 = \int_{III} L_2(f, s - b - c)H_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds, \quad I_4 = \int_{IV} L_2(f, s - b - c)H_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds.$$

By Cauchy’s Residue theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\pi i} I_1 &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma} L_2(f, s - b - c) H_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds - \frac{1}{2\pi i} (I_2 + I_3 + I_4) \\ &= x^{b+c+1} P_{13}(\log x) - \frac{1}{2\pi i} (I_2 + I_3 + I_4), \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

where $P_{13}(t)$ is the polynomial of degree 13 in t .

By Lemma 2.5, $H_2(s)$ converges absolutely in the half-plane $Re(s) > b + c + \frac{1}{2}$. Thus, for the integrals over the horizontal segments, I_2 and I_4 can be estimated as

$$\begin{aligned} &\ll \int_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}^{1+\varepsilon} L_2(f, \sigma + iT) \frac{x^{b+c+\sigma}}{T} d\sigma \\ &\ll x^{b+c} \int_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}^{1+\varepsilon} L_2(f, \sigma + iT) \frac{x^\sigma}{T} d\sigma. \end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

Furthermore, Lemma 2.1 leads to

$$\begin{aligned} I_2 + I_4 &\ll x^{b+c} \int_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}^{1+\varepsilon} T^{(\frac{25}{2} + \frac{15}{2} \times 6 + \frac{5}{2} \times 13 + \frac{4}{3} \times 21 + \frac{13}{42} \times 13)(1-\sigma)+\varepsilon} \frac{x^\sigma}{T} d\sigma \\ &\ll x^{b+c} \max_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon \leq \sigma \leq 1+\varepsilon} T^{117} \left(\frac{x}{T^{118}} \right)^\sigma \\ &\ll \frac{x^{b+c+1+\varepsilon}}{T} + x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{58+\varepsilon}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

For the vertical segment, by using Lemma 2.2 and Cauchy’s inequality, I_3 can be estimated as

$$\begin{aligned} &\ll \int_1^T \left(\left| L \left(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^4 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) L^6 \left(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \times L^{13} \left(\text{sym}^4 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) L^{21} \left(\text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \zeta^{13} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \\ &\quad \times H_2 \left(b + c + \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \left. \left| \frac{x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}}{|b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon+it|} \right| \right) dt \\ &\quad + x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} \\ &\ll x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} \int_1^T \left| L \left(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^4 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) L^6 \left(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. L^{13} \left(\text{sym}^4 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) L^{21} \left(\text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \zeta^{13} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right| \frac{1}{t} dt + x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

For convenience, we write

$$\begin{aligned} L_{2,1}(f, s - b - c) &= L(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^4 f, s - b - c) L^4(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c) \\ &\quad \times L^6(\text{sym}^4 f, s - b - c), \\ L_{2,2}(f, s - b - c) &= L^2(\text{sym}^4 f \times \text{sym}^2 f, s - b - c) L^6(\text{sym}^4 f, s - b - c). \end{aligned}$$

By a dyadic subdivision, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_3 &\ll x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} + x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} \log T \max_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T} \frac{1}{T_1} \\
 &\quad \times \left(\max_{\frac{T_1}{2} \leq t \leq T_1} \left| \zeta^{13} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) L \left(\text{sym}^4 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) L^{21} \left(\text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right| \right) \\
 &\quad \times \left(\int_{\frac{T_1}{2}}^{T_1} |L_{2,1}(f, \sigma + iT)|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\int_{\frac{T_1}{2}}^{T_1} |L_{2,2}(f, \sigma + iT)|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
 &\ll x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} + x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{58} \\
 &\ll x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{58}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

Inserting (3.4) and (3.6) into (3.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{b+c+1+\varepsilon-iT}^{b+c+1+\varepsilon+iT} L_1(f, s-b-c) H_2(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \\
 &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma} L_1(f, s-b-c) H_2(s) \cdot \frac{x^s}{s} ds - \frac{1}{2\pi i} (I_2 + I_3 + I_4) \\
 &= x^{b+c+1} P_{13}(\log x) + O\left(x^{b+c+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{58}\right) + O\left(\frac{x^{b+c+1+\varepsilon}}{T}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Setting $T = x^{\frac{1}{118}}$, we obtain

$$S_2(x) = x^{b+c+1} P_{13}(\log x) + O\left(x^{b+c+\frac{117}{118}+\varepsilon}\right).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 5. □

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